

CULTURAL INFLUENCES ON COLOR MEANINGS AND USAGE IN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN.

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Abstract. The paper explores the ways in which Russian and English use and understanding of colour is affected by historical and cultural influences. It illustrates how colour symbolism, which shows in specific metaphorical and symbolic expressions linked to social, political, and religious views, has been moulded by the two languages' divergent historical and cultural histories. The meanings and linguistic usage of colours are shaped by the cultural and historical influences of each community. Colours not only reflect sensory perceptions but can stand for societal norms, political ideologies, religious convictions, and cultural values. Understanding these influences in both languages shows how language represents speakers' worldviews and makes it easier to grasp color-based expressions.

Keywords: symbolism of colors, cultural influences, political connotations, cross cultural communication, linguistic accuracy

Cultural Influences on Color Meanings and Usage in English and Russian. The meanings and usage of color in language are profoundly influenced by the cultural and historical contexts in which these languages have developed. English and Russian, two languages with distinct historical trajectories and cultural frameworks, exhibit both universal and unique ways of employing colors metaphorically and symbolically. Colors in phraseology not only reflect perceptual experiences but also encode cultural values, political ideologies, religious beliefs, and social norms. Understanding the cultural influences on color meanings is essential for interpreting phraseological expressions and understanding how language captures the worldview of its speakers.

1. Historical and Political Influences on Color in Russian. Russian culture has been significantly shaped by its historical events, particularly the influence of Orthodox Christianity, the Russian Empire, and Soviet rule. These historical forces have left lasting impressions on the way colors are used in the Russian language.

Red (красный, krasnyy) in Russian carries strong political and cultural connotations. Historically, red was a symbol of beauty and power in pre-Soviet

Russia, as seen in expressions like красная площадь (Krasnaya Ploshchad', Red Square, meaning "beautiful square"). However, after the Bolshevik Revolution, red became indelibly linked to Soviet ideology. It symbolized revolution, the working class, and socialist ideals, appearing in the flag, state emblems, and other symbols of Soviet power. Expressions such as красный день календаря (krasnyy den' kalendarya, "red day of the calendar") refer to holidays or important political events, demonstrating how the color red became a marker of national identity and political significance.

Black (чёрный, chornyy) in Russian has historically been associated with negative experiences such as sorrow, death, and misfortune. This is partly influenced by Russian Orthodox Christianity, where black is the color of mourning and spiritual severity. The expression чёрный день (chornyy den', black day) refers to a time of hardship or disaster, reflecting the deep cultural association of black with negative life events. Black also appears in expressions that denote illegal or illicit activities, such as чёрный рынок (chornyy rynek, black market), mirroring its use in English but with a stronger emphasis on societal breakdown or moral decay.

Blue (синий, siniy) in Russian is notable for its dual meanings, one linked to extreme cold and the other to drunkenness. The phrase синий от холода (siniy ot kholoda, blue from the cold) reflects Russia's harsh climate, where extreme cold can turn a person's skin blue. However, blue also serves as slang for being drunk (синий), illustrating the unique ways in which Russian culture associates certain colors with physical states. This usage of blue reflects a societal familiarity with both the physical environment and social issues like alcohol consumption.

Russian history has had an immense impact on how colors are used metaphorically in the language, particularly during the Soviet era. The color red (красный, krasnyy), which initially signified beauty and strength, became synonymous with Soviet ideology after the Bolshevik Revolution of 1917. This association is deeply rooted in Russian national identity and historical memory. The color red became the symbol of the socialist movement, as seen in the red flag, which symbolized revolution, the proletariat, and the blood of the workers who fought against oppression. Under the Soviet regime, red was transformed into a symbol of not only political power but also everyday significance, with phrases such as красный уголок (krasnyy ugotok, "red corner"), referring to the space in Soviet homes dedicated to Communist Party propaganda. It was also common to mark significant days in the Soviet calendar in red, giving rise to

expressions like красный день календаря (red day of the calendar), which designated holidays or days of historical importance. This political transformation of color symbolism in Russian also had a profound psychological impact on Russian speakers. The pervasive association of red with Soviet ideology means that even today, red can carry both nostalgic and political overtones, depending on the speaker and context. This political connotation of color is less pronounced in English, where red does not have such a concentrated association with a particular political ideology.

2. Cultural and Religious Influences on Color in Russian. Religion has also shaped the symbolism of colors in Russian culture. The color white (белый, belyy) is associated with purity, goodness, and holiness in Orthodox Christianity, a symbolism that has extended into everyday language. For example, the phrase белый свет (belyy svet, white world) refers to life or the world, carrying positive connotations of existence and light. Similarly, белая зависть (belaya zavist', white envy) refers to a benign form of envy, where the individual does not wish harm, demonstrating the positive moral association of white.

The green (зелёный, zelyonyy) in Russian, while not as religiously charged, is often associated with youth, freshness, and inexperience. This is evident in expressions like зелёный человек (zelyonyy chelovek, green person), which refers to someone inexperienced or naive, much like the English "greenhorn." This meaning likely stems from the natural environment, where green symbolizes new life and growth, a common metaphor in many cultures but particularly relevant to Russia's rural history.

Black (чёрный, chornyy) in Russian carries deep religious connotations, particularly linked to Russian Orthodox Christianity. Black is the color of mourning and spiritual reflection, worn by Orthodox clergy and monastics to symbolize renunciation of the material world. This religious significance of black has permeated Russian phraseology, leading to expressions that emphasize suffering, hardship, or negative moral evaluations. Phrases like чёрный день (chornyy den', black day) refer to a period of extreme difficulty or misfortune, which mirrors the universal association of black with sorrow and adversity in many cultures (Mokienko & Nikitina, 1998).

Moreover, white (белый, belyy) holds a special place in Russian culture, particularly within a religious context. In Russian Orthodox Christianity, white is the color of purity, innocence, and holiness, often worn on religious holidays like Easter. This symbolism has filtered into secular expressions, where белый свет (belyy svet, white world) refers to the entirety of life or the world, often used in

a positive sense. Unlike black, white carries connotations of moral goodness and hope in both religious and everyday contexts.

These religious influences on color symbolism are less pronounced in English, where color expressions tend to be more secular in nature, reflecting the Protestant Christian tradition's lesser emphasis on symbolism and ceremonial use of color.

3. Cultural Influences on Color in English. In contrast to Russian, English color symbolism has been shaped by its own unique cultural influences, including its Protestant Christian tradition, the industrial revolution, and its role as a global imperial power. English color expressions tend to reflect a wide range of social, emotional, and psychological states, influenced by both historical events and the Anglo-Saxon cultural framework.

Red in English similarly conveys strong emotions and urgency, though with less political connotation than in Russian. For example, "seeing red" means to be extremely angry, using the color to symbolize a heightened emotional state. The phrase "red tape," which refers to excessive bureaucracy, also conveys frustration and inefficiency. Historically, red was associated with danger or warning, a symbol that carried over into modern road signs and alarms. Unlike in Russian, where red became politically charged, in English, it remains more connected to emotions and social frustrations.

Blue in English is largely associated with sadness or depression, as in the phrase "feeling blue." This usage likely stems from maritime traditions, where ships would fly blue flags to indicate mourning (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980) . The association of blue with melancholy has persisted, making it a dominant emotional metaphor in English. Unlike in Russian, where blue is linked to physical states like coldness or intoxication, in English, it is primarily a symbol of emotional suffering.

Green in English carries multiple connotations, ranging from nature and growth to jealousy and inexperience. The expression "green with envy" uses the color to signify jealousy, likely stemming from earlier associations between green and illness (such as "green around the gills"). On the other hand, green is also linked to positive associations with nature, as seen in phrases like "green energy" or "the green movement," reflecting the growing importance of environmentalism in Western cultures. These dual associations highlight the flexibility of color meanings in English, where one color can represent both positive and negative qualities depending on context. Green, on the other hand, carries a complex range of meanings in English. Historically, green was linked to fertility and

nature, symbolizing life, growth, and renewal. Over time, this meaning expanded to include new and emerging social movements, particularly environmentalism. Terms like "green energy" or "green movement" reflect the cultural importance of environmental conservation in modern Western societies. However, green in English also carries negative connotations, particularly in expressions related to jealousy and inexperience. "Green with envy" stems from ancient associations between green and illness, where jealousy was thought to cause physical sickness. Shakespeare famously used this association in Othello, referring to "the green-eyed monster" to symbolize jealousy. This blending of positive and negative meanings in green highlights the flexibility of color symbolism in English, where one color can carry multiple layers of meaning depending on context.

In English, cultural and historical events have also shaped color meanings, though with different emphases. Blue in English, for example, is most strongly associated with sadness or melancholy. The phrase "feeling blue" is widely used to express a state of emotional depression. This connection is thought to stem from naval traditions, where ships would fly blue flags to signal mourning for lost sailors. Additionally, the expression "the blues" was popularized by the development of blues music, which emerged from the African-American experience of suffering and hardship. Thus, blue in English is intimately connected to personal or collective grief, often without the physical connotations it has in Russian.

4. Shared and Divergent Color Symbolism. While both English and Russian share certain commonalities in color symbolism, such as the negative associations with black and the emotional intensity of red, there are key divergences influenced by their respective cultural histories. For example, red in Russian is deeply tied to its revolutionary past, making it a color of political power, whereas in English, red is more likely to symbolize personal emotions like anger or warning. Similarly, blue in English symbolizes emotional states, while in Russian, it reflects more physical conditions, such as cold or intoxication. Moreover, green holds different connotations in each language. In English, it is often tied to jealousy or environmentalism, while in Russian, it is linked to youth and inexperience. These divergences illustrate the importance of cultural context in determining the metaphorical meanings of colors in phraseological expressions. Despite the unique cultural influences on each language, there are some areas of overlap in how colors are used metaphorically in English and Russian. Black and red tend to carry similar meanings in both languages,

reflecting universal human experiences of danger, sorrow, and passion. Black as a marker of grief or misfortune is common in both English and Russian, seen in phrases like "black market" (illegal trading) in English and чёрный день (black day) in Russian. Similarly, red in both languages is associated with intense emotions or significant events, though the political connotations of red are much stronger in Russian due to its Soviet history. Where the two languages diverge significantly is in the meanings assigned to blue and green. As previously noted, blue in English is tied to emotional states, particularly sadness, while in Russian it is more often linked to physical conditions like coldness or drunkenness. This difference reflects the distinct ways in which each culture has metaphorically extended color terms to describe human experiences. Green, too, differs significantly, with English associating it with jealousy and environmentalism, while Russian uses green to describe youth and inexperience, without the same metaphorical ties to jealousy (Wierzbicka, 1992; Mokienko & Nikitina, 1998).

5. Impact of Color Symbolism on Translation and Cross-Cultural Communication. The cultural differences in color meanings between English and Russian have significant implications for translation and cross-cultural communication. Translating color-related expressions requires not only linguistic accuracy but also an understanding of the cultural connotations embedded in each phrase. For example, translating the English phrase "feeling blue" into Russian would be problematic, as the association between blue and sadness does not exist in Russian. Similarly, phrases like красный день календаря (red day of the calendar) would require explanation for English speakers unfamiliar with the political history that underpins the metaphor. Successful translation, therefore, depends on a deep cultural knowledge of both the source and target languages, ensuring that metaphorical and symbolic meanings are preserved in ways that resonate with the target audience. The meanings and usage of colors in English and Russian are profoundly shaped by their cultural and historical contexts. While some colors, like red and black, carry shared symbolic meanings across both languages, others, such as blue and green, diverge significantly in their metaphorical uses. These differences highlight the importance of understanding cultural influences when interpreting color-related expressions and translating them across languages. As color meanings are deeply embedded in cultural experiences, they offer valuable insights into the worldviews of different linguistic communities and play a crucial role in both language and cross-cultural communication.

From a cognitive linguistics perspective, color symbolism in both English and Russian reflects broader patterns of metaphorical thought. Humans use physical experiences to conceptualize abstract domains, such as emotions or social relations. Colors, being perceptually salient, are frequently used to structure metaphorical expressions. For example, the association between red and strong emotions (anger, love, passion) in both languages reflects a common human tendency to associate heightened physiological states (such as flushed skin) with the color red. However, the specific metaphorical extensions of these color terms are culturally conditioned, as seen in the unique uses of red in Russian political discourse or blue in English emotional discourse. The study of color-related expressions in English and Russian reveals how deeply cultural and historical factors shape the metaphorical use of colors in language. While both languages share some commonalities in their use of colors like black and red, the unique historical and cultural contexts of each language have led to divergent uses of colors like blue and green. Understanding these cultural influences is essential for accurate interpretation, translation, and cross-cultural communication. Through the lens of cognitive and cultural linguistics, we can better understand how color symbolism reflects not only perceptual experiences but also the collective values and beliefs of a society.

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